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Review Article

Sale And Marketing of Drug Considering with Different System of Medicine

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ABSTRACT

The primary goals of this study were to evaluate the progress achieved by different in the last few years through a review of scientific publications, consumer knowledge, and the distribution and sales trends of products that are ayurvedic, homeopathic, and allopathic. The reason this topic was chosen is that product distribution may have a beneficial influence on customer happiness, and the company's strategy for product promotion has a strong correlation with increased sales of items. Additionally, promotion has a high degree of impact on product sales.

INTRODUCTION

Many herbal medicines have been used safely and extensively for a very long time in India's officially recognized alternative health systems, including homeopathy, naturopathy, Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Siddha, and Naturopathy. These approaches are not in "the domain of obscurity," but have legitimately coexisted alongside allopathy. ⁽¹⁾ Marketing is the most widely utilized tactic for increasing market share. Based on study results and published and presented material, the aim of this article is to highlight pharmaceutical marketing from the industry's perspective, as well

as problems relevant to promotional strategies and how they affect doctors' prescribing habits. Before discussing pharmaceutical marketing and the issues that surround it. ⁽²⁾ Millions of Indians regularly use over-the-counter (OTC) medications for self-medication or as prescription drugs in non-allopathic systems, as well as herbal drugs as spices, home cures, and health foods. The more than 500,000 non-allopathic practitioners are trained in the medical colleges (>400) of their separate systems of health and are registered with the statutory bodies which supervise professionalism. These systems are therefore

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neither traditional nor customary herbal remedies.

⁽¹⁾ Pharma marketing, also referred to as marketing for the pharmaceutical industry, is the practice of promoting pharmaceutical and health businesses, products, and brands to both the general public and medical professionals. This category may include things like participating in online activities, giving tests, creating in-depth items, trying to raise awareness of the disease among executives, giving patients resources, organizing events and get-togethers for psychiatrists, physicians, and other medical professionals, and raising awareness of the disease among executives. Alterations in consumer tastes and behaviors, as well as upgrades in both the economy and the general status of public health, have contributed to a rise in the relevance of advertising for medicines and other health and wellness things. There is no question that this influence has had a substantial impact on the healthcare systems.⁽³⁾ In response to these discriminating customers, firms began adopting the marketing concept which is described as; "concentration on customer needs before developing the product, alignment of all functions of the company to focus on those needs and realization of profit by successfully satisfying customer needs over the long-term".⁽⁴⁾

Growth of Ayush Industry:

The research report on the Ayush Sector, prepared by the Forum on Indian Traditional Medicine under the Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS), states that the Ayush industry's market size grew to \$18.1 billion, or INR 1,49,451 Crore, in 2020. This is based on the current exchange rate between the Indian Rupee and the US Dollar. In 2014-15, the market size was \$2.85 billion, or INR 23,532 Crore, using the same exchange rate. The government has started several programs to improve international cooperation in Ayush, which will help the industry grow. These programs will support Indian Ayush manufacturers and service providers to increase

exports of Ayush products and services. These efforts will also help promote, develop, and gain international recognition for the Ayush system of medicine. They will encourage communication among people involved in the industry and help expand the global market for Ayush products. Additionally, these initiatives will support academic research and development in the Ayush sector.⁽¹⁰⁾ A report from the Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS), called 'Ayush Sector in India: Prospects & Challenges', says that the worldwide market for herbal products was worth about \$657.5 billion in 2020. This is equal to around INR 54,28,977 Crore when you convert it using the current exchange rate between the Indian Rupee and the US Dollar. Also, India's total exports of Ayush products have grown a lot, going from \$1.09 billion in 2014 to \$1.54 billion in 2020.⁽¹⁰⁾

- The Ministry has signed 24 Memorandums of Understanding with foreign countries for cooperation in the areas of homoeopathy and traditional medicine.
 - 40 agreements have been made with international organizations for joint research and academic partnerships.
 - 15 agreements have been made with international organizations to establish Ayush academic positions in other countries.
 - Ministry of Ayush has facilitated setting up 39 Ayush Information Cells in 35 international countries
- "Ayush Export Promotion Council" is registered under Section 8(4) of Companies Act, 2013 on 04.01.2022 under the Ministry of Ayush to assist the Ministry of Corporate Affairs to overcome the challenges for getting Ayush products registered outside, conducting market studies and research activities abroad.
- Memorandums of Understanding (MOU'S) on clinical research studies on Covid-

19 mitigation through Ayurveda with: Frankfurter Innovationszentrum Biotechnologie GmbH (FIZ), Frankfurt, Germany and London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine (LSH&TM), UK.

WHO-GMP (COPP) issued to 31 Ayurvedic Drug manufacturers to facilitate the export of Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani & Homoeopathy Drugs. ⁽¹⁰⁾

Parts Of Marketing A Product:

There are other factors as well; these can be characterized as functions related to the particular mission or goal of the organization. The four "Ps" of product marketing are product, price, place of distribution, and promotion; these elements have the potential to increase the degree of customer satisfaction. (5) The 4Ps system in pharmaceutical marketing Pharmaceutical marketing involves four key elements known as the 4Ps: product, price, distribution, and promotion. (5) These four components work together to form a marketing strategy that helps pharmaceutical companies successfully introduce their products to the market

1) Product

The pharmaceutical product or service that is made available to the market is taken into account by the 4Ps framework's Product aspect. This component includes all of the product's attributes, such as its functionality, appearance, and advantages for patients and medical professionals. (4) Pharmaceutical items come in a wide variety, each with distinct marketing features. Typical categories of pharmaceutical items consist of:

- prescription drugs
- over-the-counter medications
- vaccines
- medical devices

generics (copies of brand-name drugs).

When developing a marketing strategy for a pharmaceutical product, it is critical to take the target audience's unique requirements and expectations into account. For instance, it is important to highlight the drug's clinical efficacy and safety while marketing prescription medications to medical professionals. Additionally, it is critical to highlight the advantages and simplicity of use of over-the-counter medications while introducing them to customers.

2) Price:

The aspect "Price" within the 4Ps framework relates to the value that customers are willing to pay for a product. Pharmaceutical products' pricing strategies are heavily influenced by price, which affects the product's profitability as well as amount of demand. (4) A variety of pricing options are available to pharmaceutical businesses. Typical price tactics consist of:

- cost-based pricing;
- value-based pricing;
- competition-based pricing

When setting the price for a medicine, companies need to think about many things, like how much it cost to make the medicine, how other medicines compare, and what patients and doctors need. The cost of medicines is a big concern in the drug

industry because lots of patients can't afford the treatments they need. To help with this, drug companies are trying to make things better by giving discounts and helping patients with their costs. (4)

3) Place:

The Place part of the 4Ps framework involves the ways a pharmaceutical product reaches customers. These ways include pharmacies, hospitals, and other healthcare places where the product can be bought. (4) Distribution is a very important part of pharmaceutical marketing because it makes sure that patients and healthcare workers can get the products they need. When picking a distribution method, pharmaceutical companies need to think about many things, like the product's features, who they want to sell to, and what other companies are doing. For instance, medicines that need a doctor's prescription usually go through wholesalers and pharmacies, while vaccines often go through government groups. (4)

4) Promotion:

Pharmaceutical companies use different methods to tell people about the benefits of their medicines. This is called the Promotion part of the 4Ps framework. These methods include direct marketing, special sales offer, public relations, and ads. (4) There are many ways pharmaceutical companies can advertise. Some common ways are:

- using different types of media like TV, radio, newspapers, and the web to advertise
- collaborating with media outlets to generate good news stories about their products
- offering special deals or discounts;
- directly reaching out to patients and healthcare providers through email, mail, and sales people.

Pharmaceutical companies need to follow strict guidelines and rules when promoting their products, and they must also consider what is right and fair. For instance, they should not say things

about their products that could be wrong or not backed by science. This is crucial to keep patients and doctors safe and to maintain their trust. (4)

Research Methodology :

The researcher used the Doctrinal Method to structure this work. This research paper is a descriptive and analytical study. Information was gathered from secondary sources such as books, journals, articles, and online websites, all of which were properly cited. The Doctrinal Method involves organizing ideas and summaries in a systematic manner, with references taken from secondary data sources. Primary data was also used to identify specific sectors where the problem exists. Additionally, the researcher employed the empirical method by collecting information from various organizations where this practice occurs and analyzing statistics related to the issue. The growth of the Ayurvedic market in India will also be examined. The paper will also discuss the different segments of the Ayurvedic market, using statistics from various market websites.

Various System Of Medicine

1. Ayurvedic medicine
2. Homeopathic medicine
3. Allopathic medicine

1. Ayurvedic medicine: In 2023, the Indian ayurvedic products market was worth INR 748.5 billion. IMARC Group projects that the market will reach INR 3,207.6 billion by 2032, growing at a CAGR of 17% between the years 2024 and 2032. Some of the main factors that are driving the market are the rising prevalence of medical disorders, consumers' increased awareness of their health, and the simple availability of ayurvedic products through both online and offline distribution channels. (7) The Indian ayurvedic products market was valued at INR 748.5 billion in 2023

Indian Ayurvedic Products Market

Market Forecast To Grow At Cagr Of 17.6%

Fig.no.:1(Refrance :11)

Growth projection of Ayurveda product market:

The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly altered the daily lives of individuals, effectively establishing a new standard of living. (12)A notable transformation resulting from the pandemic is the heightened demand for Ayurvedic products, which has become increasingly prevalent. This surge in interest appears to be enabling the Indian Ayurveda sector to achieve its growth objectives ahead of the anticipated timeline (2019-2024). Market analysis indicates that the growing appetite for Ayurvedic products, coupled with an increase in discretionary spending, could elevate the Ayurveda market to a valuation of \$15 billion by 2023. The industry has witnessed robust growth, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 15% expected to persist until 2026. Since the onset of COVID-19, there has been a marked shift in consumption patterns. (12) Demand scenario of india and consumer behavior: For the information of the reader, AIIA14 has been set up in October 2017 as an autonomous institute under the Ministry of AYUSH, Government of India, to offer Ayurveda products and healthcare services in response to the growing global and domestic interest in Ayurveda. This institute will serve as the center of excellence, working as the premier institution for Ayurveda, integrating delivery of healthcare with education and training in the area. The FDI in the country's healthcare and wellness industry is proposed to benefit Ayurveda. " Before they turn 70, one in four Indians runs the

danger of passing away from a non-communicable disease. Every segment of the population is impacted by Ayurveda. The demand for natural remedies in the nation is rising as a result of all these causes. According to a different study, Ayurveda plays a big part in the Indian healthcare system and makes up 70% of the formal pharmaceutical industry (Bulsara and Yadav, 2018). The market will probably continue to expand. According to a WHO report, the global herbal industry is expected to reach approximately USD 5 trillion by 2050. Deshpande (2015) reports that the demand for herbal goods has been increasing at an annual growth rate of 8% between 1994 and 2001. It added that only about 35 of the hundreds of units in the industry sell for INR 500 million. As a result, the demand situation seems optimistic.(8)

Organizational Setup and Programs:

The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare established the Indian Systems of Medicine and Homoeopathy in March 1995. In November 2003, it was renamed the Department of Ayurveda, Yoga, Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha, and Homoeopathy, commonly referred to as AYUSH. (8) Following the Government's plan to focus on Indian Traditional Medicine, the Department of AYUSH became a Ministry on November 9, 2014. This Ministry is in charge of making policies and running programs to help grow, improve, and spread AYUSH healthcare systems. (8) The Ministry of AYUSH manages two main regulatory groups: the Central Council of Indian Medicine

(CCIM) and the Central Council for Homeopathy (CCH). The Ministry also has a Drug Control Cell that handles drug quality and Ayurvedic medicine regulations based on the 1940 Drugs and Cosmetics Act and its implementing regulations. The Indian Ayurvedic industry and other wellness services have been aggressively supported by the government, especially through administrative initiatives. As a result, in November 2014, the Department of Indian System of Medicine and Homeopathy was upgraded to a standalone ministry. This led to the establishment of the Ministry of AYUSH, aimed at fostering the development and dissemination of AYUSH healthcare systems. The National Health Policy of 2017 recognizes the diversity within the Indian healthcare landscape, where traditional and modern medical practices coexist. This policy emphasizes the integration of Indian traditional medicine, including Ayurveda, into mainstream healthcare. Health is identified as one of the 12 Champion Services Sectors by the Department of Commerce, Government of India. Furthermore, the National Health Policy prioritizes the integration of AYUSH, ensuring its accessibility through the co-location of public health facilities. It also highlights the necessity for standardization and validation of Ayurveda medicines, alongside the establishment of a comprehensive quality control framework for these drugs. The policy advocates for the use of digital tools to facilitate the generation and dissemination of information regarding AYUSH systems. Consequently, Indian medicinal practices like Ayurveda are receiving significant policy support, which is expected to further enhance the industry's growth. (8)

Example Of Ayurvedic Product Mfg. Company In India (9)

1. Dabur India Ltd. (Established in 1884)

Dabur India Ltd. is indeed a pioneer in the Ayurvedic business and a name trusted from inception in 1884. A multinational consumer

goods giant, the company's product portfolio is very diverse, incorporating.

Such as health supplements, personal care, cosmetics, and skincare. The flagship brand of Dabur is Chyawanprash. Though the house does distribute pharmaceutical products of other companies as well, it's primarily strong in producing an entire portfolio of Ayurveda products, hence the preferred choice for authentic Ayurvedic solutions by the consumers.

Popular Products:

- Dabur Chyawanprash: An immunity-boosting health supplement.
- Dabur Honey: Pure honey for daily consumption.
- Dabur Hajmola: Digestive tablets.
- Dabur Amla Hair Oil: Hair oil for nourishment and strength.

2. Zydus Lifesciences Ltd. (Established in 1952)
Zydus Lifesciences Ltd., an established pharmaceutical firm with a substantial presence in India, was previously known as Zydus Cadila Healthcare Ltd. The company was founded in 1952 and has a long history of innovation and contributions to healthcare. Zydus Lifesciences is largely a pharmaceutical company, although it has also made forays into the Ayurvedic market. (9)

- Nityam Churna: A natural laxative.
- Sampriti Tablets: For digestive health.
- Pancha Tulsi Drops: Immunity booster.
- Shudh Raktashodhak: Blood purifier.
- Zandu Balm: Pain relief balm.

3. The Himalaya Drug Company (Established in 1930)

With a legacy dating back to 1930, The Himalaya Drug Company has solidified its position as a leading name in herbal healthcare. Renowned for its extensive range of herbal products, the company has successfully bridged the gap between traditional Ayurvedic wisdom and modern scientific research. This unique approach has enabled Himalaya to develop effective and reliable

herbal formulations that address a wide spectrum of health concerns. The company's commitment to quality and efficacy has garnered trust among consumers worldwide. (9)

Popular Products:

- Liv.52: Liver care supplement.
- Himalaya Ashwagandha Tablets: Stress and anxiety relief.
- Himalaya Purifying Neem Face Wash: Skin cleanser.
- Himalaya Baby Care Range: Including baby lotion, shampoo, and powder.
- Himalaya Bresol: Respiratory wellness tablets.

4) Patanjali Ayurved Ltd. (Established in 2006)

Founded by the influential duo of Baba Ramdev and Acharya Balkrishna in 2006, Patanjali Ayurved Ltd. has rapidly emerged as a transformative force in the Ayurvedic industry. (9)

Popular Products:

- Patanjali Ghee: Pure cow's ghee.
- Divya Swasari Vati: Respiratory wellness tablets.
- Patanjali Aloe Vera Gel: Skin care gel.

The research was conducted using secondary data sources, which include books, reports, newspapers, websites, and similar materials. The raw data was not directly collected from the organization, which may result in discrepancies between the reported information and actual facts. Additionally, time constraints have limited the study's scope to a few specific locations or cities.

Marketing Strategy For Ayurvedic Market:

1) Local Business Listing:

Ensure your business is included in search engine business listings such as Google My Business, Bing My Business, and other business directories. Having a local presence on these listings helps you promote your brand in your local area. There are free business listing sites available, like Bing's business listing services. However, we suggest

opting for a premium business directory for better visibility and higher conversion rates.

2) Email Marketing

The more connections you build with your customers, the more you can start sending emails. Email marketing is a fantastic way to keep your customers interested in your new products and special deals. This is a very good way to promote your Ayurvedic products. Using email newsletters, you can keep an eye on your loyal customers. You can see which products are selling the most. You can also find out who is interested in buying your services. This helps you feel more confident because you learn more about your target audience. This is very important for planning how to introduce your Ayurvedic products to the market.

3) Online Advertising

Online advertising is a good way to promote your brand or product. In this type of advertising, you can use the PPC (Pay-Per-Click) model, where you pay for each click on your ad. You can also use Social Media Marketing (SMM) on platforms like Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, and others. YouTube Marketing is a great tool for any product that can benefit from showing customer reviews through video testimonials. This platform also allows you to demonstrate the quality of your product. (16)

4) Social Media Marketing

Social media marketing costs less than Google ads or traditional advertising. When customers see your posts, content, and stories, they can interact with them. (16) Your loyal followers on social media can help you reach more people than traditional advertising can. (13)

5) Ayurvedic Distribution Franchise

Ayurvedic PCD Pharma Franchise -We aim to integrate the holistic principles of Ayurvedic science into contemporary formulations, ensuring the best customer experience with herbal and Ayurvedic medicines. This includes a range of

Ayurvedic products such as herbal oils, tonics, herbal drops, and Ayurvedic supplements. To expand the reach of our herbal products, we are offering an Ayurvedic PCD Franchise business opportunity across India. We currently have several pharma distributors partnering with us for the Ayurvedic Pharma Franchise.

6) Direct Selling Business / Multi-Level Marketing

Multi-Level Marketing (MLM) is a method where salespeople make money by selling products directly to customers and by bringing in new people to join the business. This results in different levels of payment, which is why it's called "multi-level." (13)

7) Phone and Text Message Marketing

Telemarketing means calling people to tell them about your products. Here are some tips. SMS marketing is when you send special messages to customers' phones. Here's how to do it well:

8) Teaching Classes, Special Events, and Trade Shows

Teaching seminars are a great way to share information about Ayurvedic practices and products. Here's how you can use them: they can help sell more Ayurvedic products.

2. Allopathic system medicine

The word homeopathy was coined in the early 19th century by a German physician named Christian Friedrich Samuel Hahnemann. This he developed to draw a clear distinction between conventional medicine and that this homeopathy is a kind of alternative medicine. Allopathy is derived from Greek 'allows', meaning other, and 'pathia', which means 'suffer'.(18) Modern allopathic medicine owes its origin to Greco-Roman medicine and Northern European traditions Allopathy is derived from Greek roots meaning "other than the disease" Its foundation is laid on the sciences of anatomy, biochemistry, physiology, and the structure function relationship between cells, tissues, and organs(19), allopathy focuses on diagnosis,

treatment, and cure for acute illnesses via surgery, radiation, and other treatment modalities, including potent pharmaceutical drugs with major concern for toxicities(19) Allopathic medicine is another term for conventional, or modern Western medicine. This is an evidence-based system whereby doctors and other professionals deal with symptoms through traditional medications. This other side, on the other hand, is known as allopathy or modern medicine, and is given that name specifically for the global mainstream medical system based on rigorous scientific principles and evidence-based practice. It is based on a broad range of artificial substances painfully designed to interact with specific molecular targets within the body, thereby modifying physiological pathways for therapeutic effects. These new approaches in the fields of pharmacology, biochemistry, and molecular biology have made it much easier to come up with therapeutic targets and develop new drugs that are of higher efficacy and fewer in number of side effects. Researchers are involved in developing new methods for discovering and optimizing drugs because, thanks to the complexity of human biology, a great threat concerning drug resistance is growing.

We combined search terms because the domain was not well-defined by standard terminology. We employed phrases like "marketing-sales" and "marketing and sales." (23)

Benefits of allopathic medicine

1. Emergency Relief – Allopathy responds fast in emergencies by putting the condition of the patient in the right place.
2. Surgical activities are well-treated in allopathic medicine. Over here, various surgical issues are dealt with accurate and effective solutions.
3. Allopathic medicine offers a broad spectrum of antibiotics. Antibiotics can now be used in the treatment of most bacterial infections.

4. Allopathy is very effective in curing acute cases, meaning the cases that have developed rather than those that have been present for years often do this with speed and usually instantly.

5. Standardized Treatment Protocols-Allopathy being a practicing system, it has standardized treatment procedures across its practitioners.

6. Readily Available-Modern drugs are manufactured in bulk quantities which means it's ready to use at any drug store even in emergencies. Apart from that, there is a special composition made to provide instant relief in patients even from fever to joint pains.

Drawback of allopathic medicine

1. Can cause side effects – Allopathic medicine can sometimes lead to unwanted side effects. These may vary from minor discomforts to serious health complications, causing additional distress to patients.

2. Less focus on prevention – Allopathy tends to concentrate more on treating existing diseases rather than preventing them. This approach can lead to recurrent health issues.

3. Often expensive treatments – The treatments in allopathic medicine are often high-priced, making it less accessible for people with limited financial resources.

4. Over-reliance on prescription drugs – There is a heavy dependency on prescription drugs in allopathy. This can lead to drug dependency and also potential misuse.

5. Ignores holistic health approach – Allopathy primarily focuses on treating symptoms rather than the whole person. It often overlooks the holistic health approach which considers physical, mental, and social well-being.

6. Incorrect Diagnosis- may be fatal A misdiagnosed disease can turn fatal for patients as the doctors may prescribe a whole different formula to treat the ailment. Moreover, most of the time, doctors have a hectic schedule and numerous patients to attend.

Marketing Stategy For Allopathic Market:

1. Product Knowledge and Positioning: Get a thorough understanding of both your product and the market environment that it competes in. (22) Emphasizing the special qualities and benefits of your product is important, but knowing how it fits into the larger market environment gives it more strategic depth. Make use of empirical proof and clinical data to back up your product claims. Strong evidence supports your position because decision-making in the healthcare industry is becoming more and more data driven.

2. Targeted Marketing and Segmentation: Use behavioral and psychographic insights in along with demographic data to segment your target audience. Marketing strategies can be more individualized and effective when they take into account the needs and motivations of various target segments. Make good use of digital marketing channels, like email campaigns, webinars, and targeted social media ads. These systems facilitate direct contact with healthcare practitioners while providing precision targeting possibilities. (22)

3. Relationship Building: It takes more than simply sales presentations to develop relationships. Becoming a reliable resource and advisor for medical professionals is part of it. Provide value- added services such continuing clinical updates, patient support initiatives, and educational resources. Rather than concentrating only on transactional contacts, make an investment in developing long- term relationships. Sustained loyalty, advocacy, and referrals can result from a solid rapport.

4. Data-Driven Insights: Analyzing data is a valuable tool for forecasting consumer behaviour, identifying market trends, and improving sales tactics. Invest in reliable analytics systems that offer timely, actionable insights. Use machine learning algorithms and predictive analytics to

foresee changes in the industry, spot new opportunities, and tailor interaction tactics. (22)

5. Compliance and Ethical Practices: In pharmaceutical sales, compliance is not only necessary to comply with regulations but also a fundamental element of trust and honesty. To guarantee ethical behaviors, keep abreast of industry norms, best practices, and regulatory developments.

- Develop comprehensive compliance training programs that highlight the value of making moral decisions, being transparent, and abiding by promotional codes for sales staff.

6. Value-Based Selling: In a healthcare landscape focused on value, illustrate the ways in which your product enhances patient outcomes, lowers healthcare expenses, and supports quality improvement initiatives. Present value propositions that are substantiated by clinical evidence and health economic evaluations. Engage with healthcare providers to develop value-based care frameworks, outcomes-oriented contracts, and performance-driven reimbursement models. Position your product as a collaborative partner in the pursuit of superior healthcare results.

7. Educational Initiatives: Educational initiatives must be continuous and customized to meet the diverse needs of various stakeholders. It is essential to provide continuing medical education (CME) programs, webinars, workshops, and online resources that specifically target existing knowledge gaps and clinical challenges. Incorporating the insights of thought leaders, key opinion leaders (KOLs), and medical societies into educational efforts can enhance both reach and credibility. Utilizing their expertise will aid in the development of engaging educational materials and promote peer-to-peer learning. (22)

8. Adaptability and Agility: The pharmaceutical industry is in a state of continuous transformation, influenced by scientific progress, shifts in market conditions, and alterations in regulatory

frameworks. It is essential to remain adaptable by consistently evaluating market trends, competitor approaches, and customer insights. Cultivating an environment that prioritizes innovation and ongoing enhancement within your sales team is crucial. (22) Promote a spirit of experimentation, derive lessons from setbacks, and swiftly adjust to evolving market circumstances.

9. Patient-Centric Approach: Focus your sales and marketing strategies on the needs of patients. Gain insights into their requirements, preferences, and experiences during the treatment process. Create initiatives that prioritize the patient experience, aiming to improve adherence to medication, enhance educational resources, and encourage collaborative decision-making. Utilize technological advancements, including mobile applications, telehealth services, and remote monitoring systems, to facilitate patient involvement and promote self-management.

10. Measuring Success: Establish specific key performance indicators (KPIs) that correspond with your sales goals, including metrics like market share expansion, customer acquisition rates, sales conversion ratios, and customer satisfaction levels. (22) Develop comprehensive analytics and reporting systems to monitor these KPIs, assess sales performance, and analyse the effectiveness of your sales strategies. Leverage data-driven insights to refine, enhance, and promote ongoing improvement.

CONCLUSION:

Pharmaceutical research relies heavily on sales and marketing to promote the use of medications and enhance patient outcomes. Pharmaceutical firms are able to create strategies that effectively overcome obstacles and leverage opportunities by comprehending critical trends, difficulties, and best practices. It's critical to stay adaptable, creative, and dedicated to providing value to stakeholders, HCPs, and patients alike as the industry changes. Without a question,

pharmaceutical marketing has its own unique set of potential and difficulties. It is clear that non-pharmaceutical businesses do not usually employ this marketing strategy. Some strategies that focus on the core elements of marketing people, tangible proof, place, promotion, product, and price help mitigate the risks and difficulties brought on by globalization, increased competition, and the fight for dominance in the global market. Performance is essentially improved by innovation in the sector, and the Green Marketing approach has increased the standard. The pharmaceutical sector serves a diverse range of customers. On one extreme of the spectrum, patients are the ultimate consumers, while physicians and pharmacists are the clients on the other. The potential of OTC product promotion is similar to that of traditional marketing. OTC product marketing has comparable potential to traditional marketing. Allopathic and Ayurvedic medicine's potential for life-saving drugs necessitates a distinct set of tactics. Assuming that a patient will want the product and that a doctor will prescribe it, one must eventually sell a concept in these situations. In contrast to the FMCG sector, where the product meets demands, pharmaceutical marketing uses a product that satisfies customers' needs.

REFERENCES

1. Nagori K, Sharma M, Agrawal A, Agarwal AK, Sharma A, Verma H, Tripathi DK. General awareness on allopathic, ayurvedic and homeopathic system of medicine in Chhattisgarh, India. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 2011;3(4):159-62.
2. Civaner M. Sale strategies of pharmaceutical companies in a “pharmerging” country: the problems will not improve if the gaps remain. *Health policy.* 2012 Aug 1;106(3):225-32.
3. Kejariwal M, Bhat R. Marketing strategies for pharmaceutical industry—A review. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results.* 2022 Dec 22:3602-6.
4. Doucette WR, McDonough RP. Beyond the 4Ps: using relationship marketing to build value and demand for pharmacy services. *Journal of the American Pharmaceutical Association.* 2002 Mar 1;42(2):183-94.
5. Doucette WR, McDonough RP. Beyond the 4Ps: using relationship marketing to build value and demand for pharmacy services. *Journal of the American Pharmaceutical Association.* 2002 Mar 1;42(2):183-94.
6. Haider R, Mehdi A. *Cruciferous Vegetables and Cancer Prevention.*
7. *India Ayurvedic Products Market Report by Product Type (Healthcare Products, Personal Care Products), Organized/Unorganized (Organized, Unorganized), and Region 2024-2032* Report ID: SR112024A1279
8. Welch K. *What International Market Entry Strategy Should Kerecis Follow to Enter Into the Indian Chronic Diabetic Wound Market?* (Doctoral dissertation).
9. *Ayurvedic Companies in India: Its Products, History, and More | BY AYURVEDIC INDIA 04/08/2024 | (Top 10 Ayurvedic Companies In India: Products, History & More (ayurvedicindia.info)*
10. Yadava R, Arshathjyothi PS. Development and contributions of AYUSH sector-A Review. *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrated Medical Sciences.* 2021 Jul 10;6(3):57-61. | 21MAR 2023
11. *India Ayurvedic Products Market Report by Product Type, Organized/Unorganized, and Region 2024-2032 (researchandmarkets.com) (Fig.no.1)*
12. *Marketing Prospects of Ayurvedic Medicines and Products in India in the Post pandemic era I* Surbhi Varshney, Sanjay Singh Khatri (ISSN-2349-5162)
13. Jadhav HB, Sablani S, Gogate P, Annapure U, Casanova F, Nayik GA, Alaskar K, Sarwar N, Raina IA, Ramniwas S, Mousavi Khaneghah

- A. Factors governing consumers buying behavior concerning nutraceutical product. *Food Science & Nutrition*. 2023 Sep;11(9):4988-5003.
14. Kudlu C. Keeping the doctor in the loop: Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals in Kerala. *Anthropology & Medicine*. 2016 Sep 1;23(3):275-94
15. Different Marketing Strategies of Patanjali Ayurveda Ltd & it's effect on the Current Market Scenario Sayali Rewatkar¹, Senthil Kumar², Dr. Meenal Pendse
16. Ayurvedic Medicine and Online Marketing : A Review of literature *International Res Jour Managt Socio Human* 2019, isara solutions
17. Sharma Y. Consumer Behavior towards Herbal Medicine and Practices (Survey). *Journal of US-China Medical Science*. 2021;18:37-56.
18. Uma E, Mala T, Geetha AV, Priyanka D. A comprehensive survey of drug-target interaction analysis in allopathy and siddha medicine. *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*. 2024 Sep 23:102986.
19. Misra K, Sharma P, Bhardwaj A, editors. *Management of high altitude pathophysiology*. Academic Press; 2018 Jul 19
20. Uher I, Cholewa J, Kunicki M, Švedová M, Cimbolakova I, Kůchelová Z, Kimáková T, Jusková M. Allopathic and Naturopathic Medicine and Their Objective Consideration of Congruent Pursuit. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternativ Medicine*. 2020;2020(1):7525713.
21. Rogers B. Contract sales organisations: Making the transition from tactical resource to strategic partnering. *Journal of Medical Marketing*. 2008 Jan;8(1):39-47.
22. Galambos L, Sturchio JL. Pharmaceutical firms and the transition to biotechnology: A study in strategic innovation. *Business History Review*. 1998 Jul;72(2):250-78.
23. Chernetsky VV, Hughes DE, Schrock WA. A synthesis of research on the marketing-sales interface (1984–2020). *Industrial Marketing Management*. 2022 Aug 1;105:159-81.
24. Rajput K, Pandey RK. Pharmaceutical marketing: A literature review. *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*. 2022;12(2):56-63

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